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Lombok Teachers and Principals Building Resilience in Facing Earthquakes and Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

Effective leadership is needed when the organization faces difficult situations. When major earthquakes and pandemics successively hit North Lombok, the role of teachers and school principals significantly determined the resilience of the school organization's sustainability. The study aims to understand how elementary teachers and principals in Pemenang district, North Lombok regency, West Nusa Tenggara province, Indonesia built their school resilience in facing consecutive natural disasters; devastating earthquakes Covid-19 pandemic. This study focuses on how school leaders and their teams built the organization's resilience during consecutive disasters in North Lombok. The study used a qualitative phenomenology design. The data collection was conducted using semi-structured interviews, Forum Group Discussion, observations, and documentation. Purposive participants consisted of 17 teachers and two principals from 2 elementary schools. The authors found that teachers' and principals' resilience appears to be built through concrete action that the Education Office and principals facilitate to respond to challenges. It appears that concrete actions, management coordination processes, and choices of actions appropriate to the situation are essential factors in building resilience. It is concluded that efforts to build teachers' and principals' resilience must align with the existing context and situation while paying attention to various resources at all levels and considering the diversity of perspectives regarding how individuals, organizations, or communities understand and respond to situations and events such as earthquakes and pandemic.

Keywords: Leadership, Resilience, Earthquakes, Pandemic, North Lombok

1. Introduction

As a country located in the Pacific ring of fire, Indonesia is a country that has the most active volcanoes and a high potential for natural disasters (Rahma, 2018). The Indo-Australian plate crosses Indonesia in the South, the Pacific in the East, and Eurasia in the North, making Indonesia a disaster-prone country from tectonic and volcanic activities. With such conditions, Indonesian people are familiar with natural disasters such as volcanic eruptions, earthquakes, or tsunamis.

One of the large-scale disasters in Indonesia and became the focus of the research was the Lombok earthquake in 2018. The earthquake, which mainly hit the district of North Lombok, West Nusa Tenggara, has become an interest

in studying its distinctive pattern. It had an up-and-down pattern of seismicity, resulting in panic and confusion for the people who lived in the affected areas (Zulfazikra & Amir, 2020). The Lombok earthquake lasted for a relatively long period, starting at the end of July to mid-August 2018, with an unusual pattern of seismicity (shaking in the earth's crust), in the form of earthquakes with large and destructive magnitudes (seismic energy), successively and fluctuating (Zulfazikra & Kusumawati, 2020). According to Zulfazikra (2020) there were at least six earthquakes with a magnitude of more than 5.5 : [1] 29 July 2018 with a magnitude of 6.4 as the beginning of a series of earthquakes, [2] 5 August 2018 with a magnitude of 6.9 and a hypocentre depth of 34 km, [3] 9 August 2018 with a magnitude of 5.9, [4] 19 August 2018 with a magnitude of 6.3 and a hypocentre depth of 7.9 km and [5] 19 August 2018, in the evening, with a magnitude of 7.0 and a hypocentre depth of 25 km, and [6] 25 August 2018 with a magnitude of 5.5. In addition to those six earthquakes with a magnitude of 5.5 and above, the Meteorology, Climatology, and Geophysics Agency (BMKG) recorded more than 2000 mild aftershocks on Lombok island.

Based on the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) website dated 10 September 2018, these series of earthquakes brought a total death toll of 564 people, of which 467 were local people of North Lombok district. Injured victims reached 1,584 people, of which 829 were local people of North Lombok. There were 214 infrastructures such as bridges, roads, bus terminals, piers, irrigation to dams damaged and affected by the disaster, with the most damaged infrastructure occurring in North Lombok as many as 85 units. The number of schools damaged, both heavily, moderately, and lightly damaged, reached 1,194 units, of which 639 units were Elementary School buildings, 254 Early Childhood Education (PAUD) buildings, 155 Junior High School (SMP) buildings, 72 units of High School buildings, 56 units of Vocational High School buildings and 8 units of Special Schools (SLB) buildings. The earthquakes also damaged 46 markets, 105 hotels, and 566 shops. Financially, the total damage was estimated at Rp 10.1 trillion, and a total loss of Rp 2 trillion with the total funding requirement for rehabilitation was approximately Rp 8.6 trillion.

When life in North Lombok started to run normally, the region faced another disaster in a different form; the Covid-19 pandemic. Amid efforts to revive all elements of North Lombok society after the earthquake in 2018, the COVID-19 pandemic hit the country in early 2020. The communities were asked to stop all activities outside their homes, including teaching and learning activities.

To anticipate the spread of the Covid-19 virus among the world of education, governments from various countries have issued learning policies from home (Karasan & Erdogan, 2020). The Circular Letter of the Ministry of Education and Culture Number 15 of 2020 concerning Guidelines for Organizing Learning from Home in an Emergency Period for the Spread of Covid-19 was issued to fulfill students' rights to obtain educational services during the pandemic. Schools are given the freedom to manage their online teaching and learning activities (Lo Moro et al., 2020). The school closure policy affected nearly 69 million students from various levels in Indonesia. Schools were also asked to eliminate all exam activities that risk crowding out. For the first time in 3 decades, national examinations for grade 9 and 12 students were abolished (Arsendy et al., 2020).

For educators in North Lombok who are still in the recovery stage of teaching and learning activities after the earthquake, indeed, this pandemic condition has become another big challenge to face. More than 4,000 teachers and 30,000 students from 200 schools in 5 districts in North Lombok are struggling with limited school facilities and infrastructures. According to Rigianti (2020), limited network constraints are the most common challenges found in online learning. Other limitations are the lack of information technology mastery of teachers and students, inadequate facilities and infrastructure, and the high cost of technology support devices (Asmuni, 2020). The lack of educators' skills in using technology must be a big concern to be taken seriously so that learning can optimally run (Aliyyah et al., 2020).

From an economic perspective, the pandemic condition also significantly impacts North Lombok. North Lombok Regency is the entry point for foreign and local tourists to visit the famous Gili Islands, Gili Trawangan, Gili Meno, and Gili Air. The impact of the sluggish tourism sector can be seen in the policy of the North Lombok Regency Government to reduce the target of Regional Original Income (PAD) from the original Rp. 220 billion to Rp. 107.3 billion in September 2020. As stated by the Head of the Regional Revenue Agency (Bappeda) of

North Lombok Regency, most of the PAD is obtained from hotel and restaurant taxes, but unfortunately, since the Covid-19 pandemic hit the island, the local government has to close down all hotels on the three Gilis (Ulum, 2020). This condition has excluded the lack of tourist activities in Senaru village as an alternative entrance to climbing Mount Rinjani, which provides a livelihood for many climbing guide operators (Rakhman, 2020).

In the education sector, Hamdi's research (Hamdi et al., 2021) which involved elementary school teachers in Pemenang district, North Lombok, found that there was a significant difference between the satisfaction levels of primary school teachers with civil servant status (ASN) and non-civil servant status during the Covid-19 pandemic. Hamdi explained that this might happen because ASN teachers are more secure from an economic perspective regarding wages/salaries with various types of accompanying allowances than non-ASN teachers. Although the study does not describe the scope of job satisfaction, it at least shows that economic conditions during the Covid-19 pandemic affect teacher job satisfaction, and then this job satisfaction can also affect teacher performance through work motivation (Hamdi et al., 2021).

With a unique, challenging profile, devastating earthquakes followed by the Covid-19 pandemic, the North Lombok district is an ideal location to understand how educators can build self-restraint to carry out their obligations amid a prolonged disaster. The concept of resilience that will be used as a reference in this research is resilience – the capacity to adapt and bounce back amid adversity (Windle, 2011). In an organizational context, Barasa, Mbau & Gilson (Barasa et al., 2018) stated that resilience was the ability of a system to continue to realize its goals in the face of challenges and turmoil. Resilience focuses not only on an organization's ability to cope with turmoil but also on adapting and transforming. Organizational resilience is influenced by the following factors: resources, readiness and planning, information management, mentoring, governance processes, leadership practices, organizational culture, human resources, social networks, and collaboration. There are 3 (three) main streams of conceptualization of resilience in organizations: (1) resilience as an organizational feature (something the organization has), (2) resilience as a result of organizational activities (something the organization does); and (3) resilience as a measure of the obstacles or disturbances that the organization can tolerate (Ruiz-Martin et al., 2018).

However, all the disasters and crises that an organization faces, in this case, schools, are not entirely destructive. They can also be a driving force for schools to become more influential organizations in the future (Lo Moro et al., 2020). From various studies conducted in various countries, there are three good practices school leaders can do to deal with emerging challenges (D'angelo et al., 2020; Fernandez, A. A., & Shaw, 2020): [1] Implementing servant leadership, focuses on empowerment, engagement, collaboration and placing the interests of the people above personal interests, [2] Delegating leadership responsibilities to more people in the team so that they can make better quality decisions in the face of various challenges. The social complexity is just too immense for any leader to face alone. Today's leaders need one or more leadership teams whose members have broad expertise and problem-solving skills to assist in setting appropriate priorities and to guide specific organizational actions (Southwick et al., 2017), [3] Communicating well, tactically, and effectively with various stakeholders by utilizing various communication media (Fernandez & Shaw, 2020; Kurita et al., 2021).

This study aims to determine how educators from two elementary schools located in Pemenang district, North Lombok built resilience when facing the challenges of the devastating earthquakes and the Covid-19 pandemic. Pemenang district is the smallest of 5 districts in North Lombok. There are 25 primary schools in this district, with 260 teachers and principals according to North Lombok Statistics Agency, 2021 (Kabupaten Lombok Utara, 2021). In the 2018 earthquake, most districts were severely damaged, including the school buildings, so teaching and learning activities had to be carried out in emergency tents for several months. The contours of the Pemenang area, which are primarily hills and beaches, further worsen the earthquake's impact. The tourist area of 3 Gili is located in the Pemenang district. Therefore, this research is important considering: [1] Lombok Island, where Pemenang district suffered the most in the 2018's earthquake, is a disaster-prone area so that the chances for natural disasters to reoccur on Lombok Island will always be highly possible; [2] Students' learning should not stop even when a disaster strikes. The understanding gained from this research will be helpful for policymakers to decide what activities or treatment should be given to educators (in this case, teachers and school principals) so that they have the resilience to continue carrying out their duties when facing a disaster.

2. Method

This study used a qualitative method with a phenomenological approach. Phenomenological research aims to reveal the similarity of meaning which is the essence of a concept or phenomenon that is consciously and personally experienced by a group of individuals in their lives. According to Creswell (2016), phenomenological research describes the experiences or phenomena experienced by a person. So the phenomenological approach in this study was used to reveal the experiences of educators in Pemenang district, North Lombok, in building resilience when facing the earthquake disaster in August 2018, which was then followed by the Covid-19 pandemic in March 2020.

Research participants were selected using the purposive sampling method with the selection criteria: [1] working as a teacher or school principal in Pemenang district when the 2018 earthquake and covid-19 pandemic occurred, [2] Currently working as a teacher or school principal in North Lombok. With these criteria, 17 research participants were gathered: 2 principals from SDN 3 Pemenang Timur and SDN 5 Pemenang Timur; 8 teachers from SDN 3 Pemenang Timur, 6 teachers from SDN 5 Pemenang Timur, and 1 Kepala Bidang (Division Head) at North Lombok Education Office who once worked as a school principal, so the researcher used him as a critical informant to obtain a broad range of information from a helicopter view. To obtain information related to the individual resilience of the Principals and Division Head, researchers carried out semi-structured interviews. Meanwhile, researchers carried out focused group discussions for teacher participants to obtain information related to group resilience. This focus differentiation was carried out with the consideration that the Principals and Division Head are in leadership positions who will direct the people they lead, while teachers collectively are in subordinate positions who will act following the direction of their leaders.

The questions in the interviews were open to obtain information on participants' experiences when facing the earthquake in North Lombok in 2018, which was followed by the Covid-19 pandemic situation in 2020 and how they built resilience so that they were still able to carry out their roles as educators well. The question line is designed using the fact - feeling - finding - future scheme from Greenaway (2002), in the form of open questions such as the following: [1] conditions/situation at the time of the earthquake/pandemic [2] what was felt, [3] what was found, [4] what can be applied in the future under the same conditions. This scheme was chosen with the consideration that all questions were open-ended to trigger participants to issue more elaborative responses. Not all questions were forced to be answered because they depended on the natural response developed during the interview.

Data analysis began with preparing transcripts of all interview results, which were then processed with NVivo software tools to carry out the reduction and elimination process to obtain the core theme of the participants' experiences reflected in the project map image processed by the NVivo software. The core themes obtained were then analyzed by developing a textural description (the phenomena that occurred to participants) and a structural description (explaining how the phenomenon occurred) to gain meaning from the experiences of participants in building resilience when facing challenges in the student learning process when the earthquake occurred in 2018 and followed by the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020.

3. Result and Conclusion

The NVivo software generated an idea map based on words that often appeared during the interview and focused group discussions. Those words were "school", "learning", and "condition". NVivo software then generated a project map that showed an idea map of all the words that emerged during the interview and focused discussion as follows:

Figure 1: Project Map

Based on the project map above, this research focused on discussing three elements: [1] Earthquake events; discussing the conditions of the earthquake and the learning process that took place after the earthquake, [2] the occurrence of the Covid-19 pandemic; discussing the pandemic conditions and the learning process during the pandemic, as well as [3] Reflection on personal reasons; discussing things that strengthened participants to continue to carry out their roles when facing many challenges. The summary of the results of participant interviews regarding those three elements is as follows:

3.1 Earthquake Incident

3.1.1. Earthquake Condition

The first earthquake occurred on 29 July 2018 in Bayan, followed by an earthquake measuring 7.4 M on 5 August. Earthquakes occurred continuously; hundreds of small earthquakes hit Lombok island every day. The earthquake gradually stopped within six months. The earthquake's tremors were left and right and up and down, making it difficult for the affected residents to move around. After the 5 August earthquake, almost 95 % of houses in North Lombok collapsed. Most of the school buildings also collapsed, some libraries were still standing in the unstable condition. Many of the learning equipment (books, teaching aids, computers) were damaged. All of the classrooms were destroyed. The ruins of the buildings made the surrounding so dusty, since the earthquake occurred during the dry season.

3.1.2. Learning Process

The principal's first focus was on preventing teachers from becoming complacent with the existing conditions so that they could immediately go back to work to handle the situation under the coordination of the Education Office. In the first week, there was no learning process at all. According to a circular letter from the Education Office, the school principal then instructed the teachers to register students at the refugee camps. Teachers collected student data by going around the village to look for students' whereabouts while motivating the students they met to want

to study again. The school principal and teachers were given a target time from the Education Office; two weeks after the earthquake, emergency classes must be available so that face-to-face learning activities could be carried out.

After two weeks, the principal and teachers gathered to discuss how to carry out student learning activities. They agreed to form study groups at the refugee camps where a team of teachers would bring in each study group. No matter how many students were present at the post and whoever was in it, they would be invited to study, regardless of which elementary school they came from. The principal then made a schedule for the teacher team at the assigned post. To get learning tools and facilities that were destroyed/damaged by the earthquake, the principal actively sought donations from private networks, in addition to the assistance coordinated by the Education Office. On the other hand, some parents sent their children to families outside the North Lombok district. So the Education Office supported them by providing a cover letter so that the children could be accepted at a public school in a new location.

At first, the focus of the learning activities was trauma healing. They did not use traditional learning materials. Trauma healing was necessary because many children and parents were traumatized and did not want to leave the shelter due to the endless daily earthquakes, so they did not allow their children to study. Many teachers were also traumatized because they lost their houses and belongings too. The trauma healing materials were guided by non-governmental organizations (NGOs) who had expertise in handling such cases. After trauma healing was carried out, the next thing to do was prepare the learning materials. The teachers taught mixed class materials while students from various classes studied together.

Initially, the learning activities were located under the trees in the refugee camp location. However, they could not stay under the tree for long since there was a risk of being crushed by branches due to aftershocks that were still occurring frequently. One month after the earthquake, they received some tents from the national red-cross. After having a tent, learning activities were moved from the refugee camp to a tent school. However, a more appropriate and permanent learning location was needed to focus on learning activities. Approximately on the third month, the Temporary Learning Classroom (RKBS) was ready. With the RKBS, teaching and learning activities could run normally. Many NGOs and Ministries provided support to North Lombok at that time so that North Lombok became the fastest district in handling education after the earthquake. The Regent of North Lombok then received an award related to the speed of handling post-earthquake education from the Governor of West Nusa Tenggara for making all teaching and learning activities could return to normal within three months.

3.2. Covid-19 Pandemic

3.2.1. Pandemic Conditions

When teachers and school principals were organizing the learning process and enjoying the comfort of new school buildings, the COVID-19 pandemic suddenly stroke the whole nation. The pandemic conditions in North Lombok happened according to the central government's announcement in early April 2020. The pandemic was felt more severe than the earthquake because everyone was affected. During the earthquake, lots of aid came from various parties, and people from outside the island came to take care of them. While houses were destroyed and property was lost, there was never a food shortage. There was so much food at that time; it was like sleeping with instant noodles walls and pillows with rice sacks. In the pandemic, everything was complicated. Gili tourism was severely affected, so the economy became tough. Wanting to earn extra money from selling things was difficult because everyone was also struggling economically. It was also impossible to ask the local government for help, knowing that they were also in trouble; fund was limited because they needed to be diverted to handle the pandemic. Local people needed to fend for themselves. They did not know when this pandemic would end.

3.2.2. School Learning Process

Just when adjusting to new school buildings, The Ministry of Education and Culture issued a regulation on 16 March 2020 that they were not allowed to do face-to-face learning and they had to study from home (*BDR/Belajar dari Rumah*). However, BDR was not possible to run due to limited internet access. Not to mention the issue of limited mobile phones where many families only had one mobile and used by working parents so students could not study.

Principals and teachers eventually translated BDR as a home visit. The principal instructed the teachers to go around the village to visit students gathered in certain houses/bale-bale agreed with the parents. The teachers came to deliver teaching materials and distributed the Student Worksheet (LKS). The results of student work were then taken on the next visit while giving assignments and new teaching materials. For students in locations with good internet access, study assignments were given via SMS and then collected during visits. Zoom access was utterly impossible to do. This home visit was successful because the children were not going anywhere during the COVID-19 pandemic. Teachers taught mixed classes because students gathered based on location, not grade levels.

The principal's biggest challenge was how to continue to maintain the spirit of the teachers because making visits required a lot of money and effort. Efforts were being made to divert School Operational Assistance (BOS) funds for visiting purposes. However, since the amount of BOS received was small, the additional costs for teacher visits were not big enough. Currently, face-to-face learning is carried out daily up to 10.30 AM. Students take turns to come to school in each class, except 6-grade students who study normally every day because they are about to take their final exams. The learning process during the pandemic is more complicated than during the earthquake. The curriculum target cannot be completed because the learning duration becomes longer. Children become more challenging to understand teaching materials. So then schools now focus on keeping children willing to continue learning, not on achieving learning targets.

3.3. Reflection on Personal Reasons

3.3.1. Principal's Perspective

After reflecting, the things that made me able to endure are:

- 1) Before serving as principal, I worked as a teacher for quite some time. I loved working as a teacher. I enjoyed teaching in the classroom and meeting the children. There was a great longing to see children be able to learn, and so that I was trying to do whatever it took to be able to see the children continue to learn in a suffering condition after the earthquake.
- 2) I always wanted to become a teacher, for I believed this was a good field of charity. Attending school college became my priority.
- 3) I had immense devotion and discipline as a teacher. Indeed, it was our duty to become teachers under any circumstances.
- 4) My sense of responsibility as a teacher, I felt the need to know the condition of my students after the earthquake occurred; this made me dare to leave the house after the earthquake.
- 5) I was able to regulate emotions in dealing with post-earthquake trauma. Emotionally it was hard, but I thought that instead of being traumatized at home doing nothing, I had better get out of the house to do something.
- 6) My challenging teaching experience in remote areas on the previous assignments encouraged me not to give up quickly in the face of difficulties. I became accustomed to obstacles and challenges.
- 7) My desire kept me learning, for I believe there were many things I still did not know.
- 8) I received appreciation and support from the teachers at my school. They always supported me, and this inspired me to do positive things.

3.3.3 Kepala Bidang (Division Head) Perspective

After reflecting, the things that made me and the schools survive are:

- 1) My ability to encourage myself. I thought that it was my duty to pay attention to how children, teachers, and school assets could be saved after the earthquake.
- 2) Inviting teachers to think together to deal with the obstacles in front of us so that they do not keep thinking about the loss they experienced. Because if that happened, education in North Lombok would not go through any process.
- 3) The active role of the Education Office in moving schools so that they were not complacent and ready to move when a disaster occurred so that under any circumstances, teachers and principals could carry out their duties properly. I also needed to ensure that the school management process ran well so that it would not interfere with students' learning activities.
- 4) There is support from the Regent. Currently, the momentum for education improvement is good because the new Regent cares about education issues. The budget is indeed limited because everything is being used to handle the pandemic, but for 2022 we will focus on developing the quality of teachers through comparative study activities, internships, soft skills, and hard-skills training.

3.3.4. Teacher's Perspective

After reflecting, the things that made me able to endure are:

- 1) A sense of responsibility that it is the duty to be a teacher in any situation. Indeed, this has become my duty because that is all I live.
- 2) There is an attitude of mutual support and mutual encouragement from co-workers.
- 3) We wonder what will happen to our children if we do nothing. There is a great longing for us to see children learning, a strong bond between children and teachers.
- 4) Much attention from outsiders to us during the earthquake motivated me to do something. They just wanted to come all the way to take care of us all; why don't we just keep quiet?
- 5) I would feel ashamed as a local person if outsiders cared and came to help us during the earthquake; why did we as local people stay silent?
- 6) We did not feel alone during the earthquake; even though our house was destroyed, we never ran out of food, we did not worry about what we would eat the other day.

The following are some notes related to specific responses: [1] responses stating that a pandemic event was considered more complicated than an earthquake only appeared in teacher participants and did not appear at all for Principals and Division Head, [2] responses emerged from Division Head were more a lot of things related to things outside of him, because of that the reflections arising were not only about the things that made him survive, but also how to make the schools survive.

The elaboration of events shows that the earthquakes seem more memorable than the pandemics, as it can be seen from the reflection responses that specifically refer to the earthquake moments, not both occurrences or the pandemic moments. On the other hand, the occurrence of the pandemic, although it did not destroy homes and property, was perceived to be more severe than the earthquake. This happened because the earthquake had a massive disturbance intensity in a shorter period, was visible, clearly ended, accompanied by support from many parties. Meanwhile, the intensity of the pandemic is long-term, it is unclear when it will end, the invisible nature of the virus, and no sufficient support from many parties, so it feels like everything has to be faced alone.

In the case of earthquakes, Spoon's et al., (2020) study related to the 2015 Nepal earthquake appears to be in line with the statement above. The study found that apart from the traumatic experiences that occurred, the disaster recovery efforts also provided positive experiences for the well-being of individuals and groups, which aroused from a sense of togetherness as a community present together in harmony, and therefore they felt closer to one another. Likewise, the role of the principal as a leader in North Lombok in this study is seen to be very important in building this togetherness. Yukl (2003) stated that transformative leadership, in this case, carried out by school principals, would empower teachers to perform effectively by building their trust, creating a conducive climate for the development of innovation and creativity.

In the pandemic, Godinic's et al., (2020) literature review seems to explain the above statement. The study concludes that economic uncertainty in the pandemic will result in job uncertainty, resulting in identity disturbances, namely conditions that are not in harmony with one's identity with the new reality that emerges, which will then reduce psychological well-being. Unfortunately, not everyone understands how to deal with (coping strategies) uncertainty during this pandemic, which can potentially produce mental health disorders during the pandemic (Rettie & Daniels, 2020). The Indonesian Mental Medicine Specialist Association (PDSKJI) survey dated 14 May 2020 supported this view. Their data stated that of 2,364 participants from all over Indonesia, 77% experienced psychological trauma, 69% experienced psychological problems, 68% experienced anxiety, and 67% experienced depression during the pandemic. Of those who were depressed, 49% even thought about the death.

The elaboration of resilience shows that the resilience of teachers and principals appears to be built as a process through concrete action that the Education Office and principals facilitate to respond to challenges in a situation. It appears that concrete actions, management coordination processes, and choices of actions appropriate to the context of the situation are essential factors in building the resilience of teachers and principals. This is in line with the study of Sun & Stewart (2007), which states that resilience needs to be seen as a process built through interactions between individuals, the social environment, and the wider community. Ungar's study (2004) also states that resilience needs to be seen as a social construction influenced by many multidimensional factors that each has its uniqueness. Furthermore, Ungar (2008) states that resilience is a dynamic interplay between individuals and their resources. Wherein the context of adversity, resilience is the individual's capacity to navigate in order to respond to psychological resources, social, cultural, and physical resources that exist for their well-being, as well as the capacity to individually and collectively negotiate together to ensure that these resources are present and shared following the context of the existing situation and culture.

The elaboration of reflection and personal reasons shows that the ability to find personal meaning from what is done seems to be an essential factor in building individual resilience of teachers and principals (who in this study are principals who used to be teachers). This is in line with Hansen's 1995 study in Gu (2018), which states that teacher resilience is related to one's strength and belief in one's vocational commitment as a teacher, where a sense of calling (inner calling) to become a teacher and a commitment to serving is a differentiator for the teaching profession if compared to other professions and occupations. Furthermore, Brunetti 2006, in Gu (2018) defines teacher resilience as a quality that allows teachers to maintain their commitment to teaching and doing other things related to teaching, apart from the challenges and obstacles that arise repeatedly (a quality that enables teachers to maintain their commitment to teaching and teaching practices despite challenging conditions and recurring setbacks). If it is related to the point of resilience as a process (Gu, 2018), then it states that the resilience of teachers is specific and contextual - not only influenced by the context and situation of the school where teaching and classes are faced, but also the broader context and professional situation in which they live. The context of this research is how the policies and treatment of structural officials from the Education Office to teachers.

This research should be seen as an initial effort to understand the dynamics of building resilience in the context of education in a prolonged disaster situation, where resilience is seen from the separate realm of teachers and school principals as individuals, as well as the social domain of teachers and principals as part of the school organization. There are several limitations of this study, including: [1] the limited number of participants: only two elementary school principals from the same district, [2] did not involve students and parents as beneficiaries of education, and [3] a list of questions has not differentiated between individual resilience and group resilience. With the availability of a longer time, this limitation can be corrected through the following: [1] increasing the number and expanding the levels of schools involved, by including junior and senior high schools, so that the analysis can include education level variables, [2] expanding the research area to districts in North Lombok Regency, so that the analysis can include location variables, [3] separate the constructs of individual resilience from group resilience, so that the mapped dynamics become richer, [4] add other constructs, such as transformational leadership so that the analysis becomes more affluent, and [5] strengthen the research design, such as using a qualitative grounded theory approach, or making it a mixed method.

Regarding the implications, seeing resilience as a process also means that resilience can be built based on a conscious effort designed in a structured manner. From the answers of research participants, it appeared that they

felt a more significant challenge in the pandemic when compared to the occurrence of the earthquake. In response to this, the local government of the North Lombok Regency or the West Nusa Tenggara Province through the related offices may consider strengthening the resilience of teachers and school principals so that they will be able to carry out their roles optimally during this pandemic. Efforts to strengthen resilience can be in individual training programs accompanied by community assistance, with participants involving various relevant stakeholders in the community.

4. Discussion

Resilience as a process seems to embed to an event. Thus, efforts to build resilience must align with the existing context and situation while paying attention to various resources at the individual, organizational, or community level. Moreover, efforts to build resilience need to consider the diversity of perspectives regarding how individuals, organizations, or communities understand and respond to situations and events. At the individual level, inviting individuals to seek personal meaning for what they do has a vital role in building resilience.

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